

SYNTHESIS OF BIOFLAVORS USING MICROBIAL LIPASES**Amita Madhukar Kocharekar*, Meenal Shriniwas Dukhande**¹Department of Microbiology, Parle Tilak Vidyalaya Association's Sathaye College, Vile Parle, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India²Department of Microbiology, Guru Nanak Khalsa College, Matunga, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India*Corresponding author: amita5292@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Utilization of bioflavored fruit drinks, and food articles have been increased in past few decades. Exotic flavors, and new ethnic forms of traditional flavors add distinctive aroma to the consumable products. Flavor usage plays an important role in packaged food products and, beverages in all geographic regions and there is a huge economy market associated with it. Esters are mainly used as flavoring compounds and have a very sweet fruity smell. Lipases are versatile catalysts playing a major role in advancing research in cosmetic industries and, food industries as compared to any other enzymes. Microbial lipases have been effectively utilized for direct esterification reactions in organic solvents to produce varied bioflavoring compounds. The esters produced from long chain fatty acid and short chain fatty acid have been used in food, detergent, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries. In the present study, ability of microbial lipases to esterify different alcohols and acids were studied. Different combinations of acids and alcohols were used and esters having fruity flavor were synthesized using lipase enzyme. Gas chromatography elucidated these esters as ethyl acetate, butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, isoamyl acetate, ethyl butyrate, butyl butyrate and, octyl acetate. All the biosynthesized esters have prospects as bioflavoring agent in food industries and, as fragrances in cosmetic industries.

Keywords: Bioflavor, Lipase, Esters, Cosmetic, Aroma.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Bioflavors are organic compounds which are manufactured using microorganism or plant cells or their enzymes. Flavor is the most significant factor influencing the sensual quality of food. It has an impact on consumer preference and the approval of food products. Flavoring compounds are usually volatile acids, esters, aldehydes, ketones, and alcohols [1].

Esters are formed by the condensation reaction between a carboxylic acid and an alcohol. Esters of short chain fatty acids and alcohols are used as flavoring agents in the food industries and as fragrances in the cosmetic industries. Fruity flavors are of most significance due to increasing demands of food products, confectionaries and, beverages having fruits mixed in it. Conventionally, the flavor esters have been extracted from natural materials and these compounds are labeled as organic. Plants are used to extract flavors. The composition of flavor esters and other compounds range from single to complex substances. Their chemical structures are elucidated by modern sophisticated techniques like mass spectroscopy, NMR, etc. However, the flavor active compounds obtained by extraction methods are

expensive due to their low content in natural resources. Alongside their production is dependent on various factors like climate and temperature which are difficult to control. Advancement in organic chemistry research have made it feasible to obtain concerned compounds in high quantities by using chemical synthesis. High yield is obtained by applying cheap chemical catalysts but high energy consumption, and environmental hazards generated during the synthesis reactions are of major concern. Further, the formation of chemical wastes makes this method harmful to the environment. Due to the above-stated downsides and the consumers increasing interest in natural products, research has been directed to find appropriate alternative strategies for producing the natural flavors. Various biotechnological techniques to produce flavor compounds have been developed. Research has shown that microbes can be used to produce aromas and fragrances. An alternative method for synthesis of flavors is based on de novo microbial processes or using microbial enzymes [2].

Lipases (triacylglycerol acylhydrolases; EC. 3.1.1.3) also known as serine hydrolases, are water soluble organic solvent tolerable enzymes that catalyze hydrolysis of

carboxyl ester bonds present in triacylglycerols to release free fatty acids and glycerol. These enzymes additionally accelerate other chemical reaction such as aminolysis, alcoholysis, acidolysis, esterification, and transesterification. The natural substrates for lipases are long or short chain triacylglycerols, which have very low solubility in water and the reaction is catalysed at the lipid-water interface. Under micro aqueous conditions, lipases catalysed reverse reaction, leading to esterification and transesterification [3]. Ester synthesis reactions works on the principle of law of mass action to drive equilibrium in the direction of synthesis by removing the water generated during the reaction. Thus, synthesis of esters catalysed by lipase occurs at low concentration of water. Studies have reported that lipases works on the principle of Michaelis-Menten kinetics, ping-pong bi-bi mechanism [4].

Lipase always have been used as an alternative source for production of flavoring compounds. It has the property to esterify different alcohols and acids; and transesterify vegetable oils, fats, and waste oils into esters. Esterification is the formation of an ester from an acid and alcohol, transesterification is the switching of an existing ester with alcohol fragment for another ester. Lipases are among the most versatile enzymes which are gaining importance because of many reasons. They do not require cofactors, they remain active in organic solvents, and they are regio and stereo selective towards the substrates. Regio and stereo selectivity is the ability of enzyme to differentiate between primary, secondary, and tertiary alcohols. Understanding this can help the researcher to modify the substrate in order to get vivid products [5].

Lipases are found throughout animal, plant kingdom, and in prokaryotes including bacteria and archaeobacteria. Lipase from plant origin is hardly explored in research because of its scarce availability. However, microbial lipases are more useful since they have great variety of catalytic activity and are easy to manipulate genetically and capable of rapid growth on inexpensive medium. Furthermost, microorganisms are not affected by seasonal fluctuations and can be used throughout the year. Bacterial lipases are preferred over fungal lipases because of their higher activities over neutral optimum pH. To enhance the enzyme yield and its activities, genetic and environmental manipulations can be performed more readily on bacterial cells than any other due to their short generation time, their simple nutritional needs and ease of screening methods [6, 7].

In the present study, ability of microbial lipase to esterify

different alcohols and acids were studied. Different combinations of acids and alcohols were used and esters having fruity flavor were synthesized using lipase enzyme. To detect ester, hydroxyl amine test was used. Presence of esters was further confirmed using Gas chromatography.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Enzyme

Lipase enzymes from *Bacillus altitudinis* (7929.94 Units/mg), *Candida antarctica* (11164.7 Units/mg), *Candida rugosa* (9287.58 Units/mg), *Staphylococcus hominis* (6321.11 Units/mg), Culture M (6309.4 Units/mg), and Culture N (4390.07 Units/mg), were used in this study.

2.2. Lipase catalysed esterification of acids and alcohols

To synthesize fruity esters, different combination of acids and alcohols as mentioned in table no.1 were carried out with all the purified lipases. The reaction mixture was prepared consisting of 10 mL of 1M acid and 10 mL of 1 M alcohol followed by addition of 1 ml of lipase enzyme in sterile flasks. Incubation was carried at 35°C and 155 rpm. Appropriate control was also maintained containing acid and alcohol with no lipase. After incubation, the reaction mixture was filtered through Whatman filter paper no.1. The filtrate was used as sample for confirming the ester formed using hydroxyl amine test.

2.3. Detection of esters

2.3.1. Hydroxyl amine test

Samples were checked for presence of ester by using hydroxylamine test of Holman (1961) with some modifications. 1 mL of standard ester (isoamyl acetate) was used as positive control. Hexane was used as negative control and filtrate from above reactions were used as test samples. 1 mL of sample was mixed with 1 mL of hydroxylamine hydrochloric reagent. All the tubes were incubated at 50°C for 10 minutes followed by addition of 1 mL of ferric chloride reagent. Red brown or orange coloration indicated positive results whereas yellow coloration indicated negative result [8].

2.3.2. Thin layer chromatography

TLC is a preliminary method used to identify the esters. Silica plates were prepared in laboratory. For this, slurry was prepared by constantly mixing silica powder and water in 1:2 ratio. This slurry was evenly spread on grease free glass slides. Silica plates were dried at room

temperature and activated before use by heating in oven for 2 hours at 110°C. On each silica plate, one test and one standard ester samples were spotted. TLC was done for ethyl acetate, isoamyl acetate and butyl acetate due to availability of its standards.

Hexane: ethylacetate in 3:1 ratio was used as solvent system. Iodine crystals were used as the developer[9]. Rf value was calculated using the following formula:

$$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance travelled by solvent}}{\text{Distance travelled by solute}}$$

Table 1: Different combination of acids and alcohols and their respective esters with its occurrence in natural food/beverages

S. No.	Acid	Alcohol	Ester	Type of flavor
1.	Acetic acid	Ethyl alcohol	Ethyl acetate	Grapes, cherry
2.	Acetic acid	Methyl alcohol	Methyl acetate	Rum, wine, whiskey
3.	Acetic acid	Propyl alcohol	Propyl acetate	Pear, banana, honey
4.	Acetic acid	Butyl alcohol	Butyl acetate	Ripe banana
5.	Acetic acid	Isobutyl alcohol	Isobutyl acetate	Banana
6.	Acetic acid	Isoamyl alcohol	Isoamyl acetate	Banana
7.	Acetic acid	Octanol	Octyl acetate	Orange, mushroom, waxy
8.	Formic acid	Ethyl alcohol	Ethyl formate	Rum, raspberries, wine
9.	Formic acid	Propyl alcohol	Propyl formate	Rum, berry
10.	Formic acid	Butyl alcohol	Butyl formate	Plum, rum, brandy
11.	Formic acid	Isobutyl alcohol	Isobutyl formate	Rum
12.	Formic acid	Isoamyl alcohol	Isoamyl formate	Apple, wine, fatty
13.	Formic acid	Octanol	Octyl formate	Oily, orange, waxy, citrus
14.	Butyric acid	Ethyl alcohol	Ethyl butyrate	Pineapple, apple
15.	Butyric acid	Methyl alcohol	Methyl butyrate	Apple, banana, dairy, acidic
16.	Butyric acid	Propyl alcohol	Propyl butyrate	Apricot, rancid, pineapple
17.	Butyric acid	Butyl alcohol	Butyl butyrate	Pineapple, rip fruits, banana
18.	Butyric acid	Isobutyl alcohol	Isobutyl butyrate	Pineapple, berry, cherry, apple
19.	Butyric acid	Isoamyl alcohol	Isoamyl butyrate	Apricot, pear, banana, melon

2.3.3. Gas Chromatography

Samples showing positive results for hydroxyl amine test were further confirmed by gas chromatography associated with high resolution mass spectrometry (GC-HRMS). Positive samples were sent to Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility (SAIF), IIT Powai, Mumbai for GC-HRMS analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Lipase catalysed esterification of acids and alcohols:

Samples were checked for presence of ester using hydroxylamine test. The basis of the detection by this test, is that the reaction of the ester with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in alkaline pyridine solution results in the formation of corresponding hydroxamic acid of ester. This further reacts with ferric chloride to form orange/red coloured ferric hydroxamate complex.

Out of the combinations mentioned in table no.1, the lipases were able to catalyse synthesis of esters such as butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, ethyl acetate, isoamyl acetate, butyl butyrate, ethyl butyrate, octyl acetate and

butyl formate. Esters were confirmed using GC-HRMS. Results are as shown in table 2.

Lipases act at the interface between hydrophobic and hydrophilic regions. Lipase enzyme has the nucleophile histidine acidic residue. This acts as the catalytic site, which is often buried in the molecule, surrounded by relatively hydrophobic residues. A helical polypeptide structure acts as a cover, making the site inaccessible to solvents and substrates. It may also prevent proteolytic activity of the catalytic triad, protecting the enzyme. The trend of interfacial stimulation is linked to the reorientation of the alpha helical lid structure, increasing the hydrophobicity of the surface in the vicinity of the active site, and exposing the site. The opening of the lid may be initiated upon interaction with an oil/water interface [10].

In the present study, all the lipases were specific in using acetic acid as the acidic substrate in comparison to formic and butyric acids. However, *Candida rugosa* lipase and *Candida antarctica* lipase were also able to utilize butyric acid. Thus, it can be concluded that lipases are more specific to two carbon acid and less specific to four

carbon acid and non-specific towards one carbon acid. Out of the seven alcohols used as substrates, lipases were specific towards ethyl, butyl, isobutyl, isoamyl and octyl alcohols. It was not specific towards one carbon-methyl alcohol and three carbon- propyl alcohol. Lipase

from *Candida rugosa* was very robust in catalysing synthesis of six different esters. However, other lipases had also catalysed esterification reactions producing different types of esters.

Table 2: List of microorganisms producing various esters catalysed by lipases.

S. No	Source of lipase	Synthesized esters	Total number of esters
1.	<i>Bacillus altitudinis</i>	Ethyl acetate, isoamyl acetate	2
2.	<i>Candida antarctica</i>	Butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, isoamyl acetate, ethyl butyrate	4
3.	<i>Candida rugosa</i>	Isobutyl acetate, isoamyl acetate, butyl butyrate, ethyl butyrate, octyl acetate, butyl formate	6
4.	Culture M	Isoamyl acetate	1
5.	Culture N	Butyl acetate, isoamyl acetate	2
6.	Pancreatic lipase	Butyl acetate	1
7.	<i>Staphylococcus gallinarum</i>	Butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, isoamyl acetate	3
8.	<i>Staphylococcus hominis</i>	Butyl acetate	1

a) positive control, b) negative control and test samples, c) butyl acetate, d) methyl acetate, e) isoamyl acetate

Fig. 1: Esters detected by hydroxyl amine test

Dahlan and et al in 2005 had studied synthesis of citronellyl butyrate by esterification reaction catalysed by lipase from *Candida rugosa* in a continuous packed bed reactor using hexane as solvent. The optimum conversion was obtained at a flow rate of 1mL/ min, temperature of 50°C and pH 7.5. At higher temperature and extreme pH, biocatalyst was rapidly deactivated with respect to time. Citronellyl butyrate has a strong sweet fruity floral flavorlike green citrus linalool and hence is used mainly in baked goods, frozen dairy products, candy, gelatins and puddings, non-alcoholic beverages, etc [11]. Bezbradica in 2006 had studied specificity of *Candida rugosa* lipase to catalyse

synthesis of short chain flavor esters such as pentyl propanoate, isopentyl butanoate and butyl butanoate. The highest yield of 90 % was obtained after 20 hours for these esters. They also observed decreased in enzyme activity with increase in carbon chain of fatty acids and alcohols [12].

Jin and et al in 2015 had developed a recombinant *Pichia pastoris* displaying *Candida Antarctica* lipase B. This was further used to catalyse the synthesis of geranyl butyrate with geraniol and butanoic acid as substrates. Lipase concentration of 20.9 g/L, geraniol concentration of 0.57 mol/L, butanoic acid concentration in molar ratio 1:21:1 and water activity of 0.53 were found to be optimum for the estersynthesis. When the esterification reaction was scaled up in batch condition, 97.87 % of geraniol conversion rate in 200 mL was obtained [13]. Sini Shankar and et al in 2013 have used lipase in both free and immobilized form from *Candida antarctica* to catalyse the esterification of lauric acid with n- butanol. Maximum esterification of 96.36 % was achieved using n-butanol to lauric acid molar ratio of 1: 0.7. Butyl laurate is extensively used as diesel additives, textile wetting agent, oiling agent in leather industry and in cosmetic formulations. It is also a component of flavor compositions in apricot and peach [14]. Pereira and et al in 2003 had studied esterification reactions catalysed by *Candida rugosa* lipase and animal porcine pancreas lipase. Respective lipase was immobilized on chitosan support by physical adsorption. Best result was obtained by microbial lipase in catalysing synthesis of n-butyl butyrate. Esterification activity of 83.30 % was

obtained with microbial lipase and 31.90 % with animal lipase [15].

Pooja Singh and et al 2014 had studied lipase from *Candida antarcticato* produce different flavors such as geranyl acetate (rose), citronellyl acetate (lemon), and iso amyl acetate (banana). The results indicate that 79 % conversion was obtained with this lipase [16]. Pentyl valerate was synthesized biocatalytically using *Candida rugosa* lipase immobilized in microemulsion based organogels by Raghavendra and et al in 2014. Pentyl valerate is one of the ester that is used to replace flavor of apple and pineapple [17]. Krishna and et al in 2001 had synthesized isoamyl acetate using immobilized lipase from *Rhizomucormiehei*. Yield above 80 % was obtained [18].

3.2. Detection of esters

3.2.1. Thin layer chromatography

Esters detected by hydroxyl amine test were further analysed by silica gel thin layer chromatography. R_f values were calculated as shown in table 3. On comparing the R_f values of samples with that of known esters, the ester present in the samples were identified to be isoamyl acetate, butyl acetate, and ethyl acetate. Results are presented in fig. 2.

Habulin and et al in 2006 had analyzed sugar esters qualitatively by thin layer chromatography. TLC analysis was performed on silica gel plates 60F 254 using chloroform: methanol: acetic acid: water (70:20:8:2) as

the developing system. The plates were sprayed with 50% sulphuric acid and heated at 110°C for 5 min [19]. Pabai and et al in 1995 had used Silica gel 254 to detect transesters of butter catalysed by lipase from *Pseudomonas fragi* [20]. Finkbeiner and et al in 2015 had used TLC to analyse lipase catalysed transesters. Silica gel 60 LC plates were used. The plates were developed in chloroform: methanol: acetic acid mixture in the ratio of 65:15:2 [21].

Lane 1 is standard and lane 2 is sample

Fig. 2: Thin layer chromatography for isoamyl acetate, butyl acetate and ethylacetate (Right to left)

Table 3: R_f values of esters

	Isoamyl acetate		Butyl acetate		Ethyl acetate	
	Standard	Sample	Standard	Sample	Standard	Sample
Distance travelled by solvent	4.3 cm	4.3 cm	3.8 cm	3.8 cm	4.9 cm	4.9 cm
Distance travelled by solute	3.9 cm	3.9 cm	3.5 cm	3.5 cm	4.7 cm	4.7 cm
R_f	0.9	0.9	0.92	0.92	0.95	0.95

3.2.2. Gas chromatography

The presence of esters in all the samples in this study giving positive results for hydroxylamine test, were further confirmed using gas chromatography coupled with high resolution mass spectrometer. The description of the instrument and analysis system is as follow:

Manufacturing company: Aligent gas chromatography
Capillary column: Fused silica capillary column, BPX5 Neat, 30 m x 250 μ

Detector: Mass spectrometer detector.

Column temperature: Programmed to increase from 50° C to 250° C at 8° C/min rise.

Carrier gas: Helium.

Sample injection volume: 1.0 μ L with split ratio of 10:1.

Fig. 3 to 8 depicts GC-HRMS results.

In the present study, esters samples in the reaction mixture were confirmed using GC-HRMS. The mass spectra of sample esters were compared with library search. GC-HRMS analysis showed presences of butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, ethyl acetate, isoamyl acetate, butyl butyrate, octyl acetate. Gog and et al in 2009 had used GC to analyse fatty acid methyl esters of cocoa butter formed from olive pomace oil. The reaction was catalysed by porcine pancreatic lipase. Agilent 690 series gas chromatograph was used by them [22]. Analytical detection of 2-Phenethyl alcohol-derived

fatty acid esters was done using GC-MS and GC-FID by Li and et al in 2014. They also studied the same using

TLC on pre-coated 0.2 mm Merck silica gel 60 F254 plates [23].

Fig. 3: a. Mass spectra of butyl acetate, b. Library search of butyl acetate

Fig. 4: a. Mass spectra of isobutyl acetate, b. Library search of isobutyl acetate

Fig. 5: a. Mass spectra of ethyl acetate, b. Library search of ethyl acetate

Fig. 6: a. Mass spectra of isoamyl acetate, b. Library search of isoamyl acetate

Fig. 7: a. Mass spectra of butyl butyrate, b. Library search of butyl butyrate

Fig. 8: a. Mass spectra of octyl acetate. b. Library search of octyl acetate

4. CONCLUSION

Lipase catalysed esters can be used as bioflavors in food industries and as fragrances in cosmetic products. In the

present study, lipases were able to catalyse synthesis of ethyl acetate, butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, isoamyl acetate, ethyl butyrate, butyl butyrate and octyl acetate.

Butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate and isoamyl acetate are found to be present in bananas, pineapples, and apples. Thus, these can be used as alternative to artificial chemical flavors in food and bakery articles. They are also used as synthetic food flavorants in ice-creams, candies, and cheese. Ethyl butyrate and octyl acetate are used as artificial flavoring agents resembling oranges, grapes, and other citrus fruits. Ethyl acetate and butyl acetate are used in formulation of nail polish, nail polish remover and other manicuring products.

5. REFERENCES

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